

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№10

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025

oktyabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 – Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА LIBRARY.RU

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 422 sahifa.
2025-yil, 19-oktyabr,

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

JAHON MOLIYA TIZIMIDA “YASHIL” MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANISHINING MUAMMOLARI VA SHARTLARI	12
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
EKOLOGIK MIGRANTSIYANI MINTAQAVIY MIQYOSDA MUVOFIQLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI	18
Bahtiyor Ismoilov Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li, Kadirova Zulayxo Abduxalimovna	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BANK XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH HOLATI	25
Davletova Nilufar Tulanovna	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA MINTAQANI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	30
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI	37
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
MAHALLIY XOMASHYO BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	46
Sultanov Dilshod Normamatovich	
IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA INSON KAPITALIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	50
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
O‘QITUVCHILAR VA TALABALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION TA‘LIM DASTURLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISHDA XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHUV MEXANIZMLARI	62
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA‘RIDAN FOYDALANGANLIK UCHUN SOLIQLARNING ILMIY-TADQIQOTLAR SHARHI	68
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o‘g‘li	
RESPUBLIKA IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTIDA OLIY TA‘LIMNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINING O‘RNI	74
Jonuzokov Mirzabek Kulmamatovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	80
O. Nurmuradov	
ICHKI AUDIT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA BUXGALTERIYA MA‘LUMOTLARINING ICHKI AUDIT JARAYONIDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	85
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li, Muxitdinov Shoxijaxon Xudoyor o‘g‘li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	90
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
KORPORATIV TUZILMALARDA INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	95
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Raxmatov Faxriddin Xasanovich	
GLOBAL RIVOJLANISH JARAYONIDA SUG‘URTA XIZMATLARINI ISLOH QILISH MASALALARI	99
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o‘g‘li	

DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	103
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA ERISHISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO'LLASH METODOLOGIYASINING AHAMIYATI	109
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ КАК ФАКТОР КОНКУРЕНТНОГО ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА.....	115
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURSLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISHGA OID TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY TAHLILI.....	123
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINI MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH: XULQ-ATVOR IQTISODIYOTI VA PROGRESSIV TARIFLARNI LOYIHALASH	129
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
DAVLAT RAQAMLI LOYIHALARI: UZINFOCOMNING TA'LIM TIZIMI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA QO'SHGAN HISSASI	134
Raxmatxo'jayev Axrorxo'ja Akmal o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПАСПОРТОВ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ.....	140
Мансурова Сайёра Бахтияровна	
BANK XIZMATLARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	148
Xolikova Oydin Olimjonovna	
PNEVMOMEXANIK YIGIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI XUSUSIYATLARI	153
Jumaniyazov Kadam, Salimov Shuhrat Halimovich, Nazarov Ramazon Anvarovich	
GREEN INDUSTRY AND THE ECONOMY OF ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY CONSTRUCTION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND UZBEKISTAN'S OPPORTUNITIES.....	158
Mansurova Sayyora Bakhtiyor kizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAHLILI	166
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING MIKRO VA MAKRO TUZILMALARI, ULARNING FUNKSIONAL METADOLOGIK TAMOYILLARI.....	171
Z.Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT ULUSHI MAVJUD KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBADAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	176
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARJATLARINI OG'ISHISHLARI VA ULARNI TAQSIMLASH	183
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СТОИМОСТИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ И ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ АУТСОРСИНГА	186
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYASI.....	193
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TASHKILYIY MEXANIZMLARI.....	198
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLARNI JALB QILISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	203
Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmatamat o'g'li	

MEHNATGA LAYOQATLI TRANSPORT SOHASIDAGI AHOLINI ISH O'RINLARI BILAN TA'MINLANGANLIK HOLATINI TAHLILI	207
Abdullayeva Nigora Shamsiddinovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK SOHASINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI	212
Mdraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI DIVERSIFIKATSIIYASI VA GAROV TA'MINOTI SIFATINING BANK BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	220
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYASI DOIRASIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	226
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMATLARNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KLASTERLI MEXANIZMI TAHLILI	232
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TUZILMALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	236
Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
XALQARO SAVDONING RIVOJLANISHI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	242
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING YANGI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHGA QARATILGAN NAZARIY JIHATLAR	247
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA BOJXONA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	254
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
DAVLAT TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI YURITISH	262
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdugarimovich	
РАЗРАБОТКА ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ КРЕАТИВНЫХ ИНДУСТРИЙ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКУЮ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН	273
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
A NEW STAGE IN THE APPLICATION OF MARKET MECHANISMS TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	285
Ibrayim Maxkamov	
RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH ORQALI SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	291
Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIDA DXSH ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI	297
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH	301
Shaymanov To'liqin Mahmayusupovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЦИФРОВЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В НАЛОГОВОМ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ	306
Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
СИНТЕЗ НЕЧЕТКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕПЛОЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	311
Бахриева Хуршида Аскарходжаевна, Сафаров Шохрух Шарофович, Бахрамов Муҳаммадали Ералиевичасистент	
ШАНХАЙСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА КАК КАТАЛИЗАТОР ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕЛЕЙ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	319
Базарова Гулнара Гуламовна	

O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARINING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA BANK KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	323
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QUESTIONS ABOUT THE STUDY OF PERFORMANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF APPLICATION OF LOADING AND EXTRACTING EQUIPMENT	327
Azamat Umirzokov	
MATOLARNING HAVO O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI KORRELATSION TAHLILI.....	334
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASHNING AFZALLIKLARI	339
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
IKKI QATLAMLI ARALASH TOLA TARKIBLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMASINI OLIISH USULI	343
Usnatdinova Elmira Faxratdinovna, Mirusmanov Baxtiyor, Abdurahimova Fazilat Abdullayevna	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYATI ORGANLARIDA ENG ILG'OR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARINING OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	347
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: CROSS-SECTORAL ANALYSIS.....	354
Jumayeva Kamola Azimjonovna, Khasanova Iroda Azizbek kizi	
KORXONA INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY MASALALARI XUSUSIDA	362
Ilyasova Barno Axmadovna	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI O'ZLASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	371
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH ASOSIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	378
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASHDA EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	385
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY KONSEPTUAL MEKANIZMLARI.....	392
Jalolov Abbosxon Ravshanxon o'g'li	
TEPKI UZELI KONSTRUKTIV XOSSALARI TAHLILI	398
Bozorova Farida Maxmudjonovna	
НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ОБЪЕДИНЕНИЯ АКЦИЗНОГО НАЛОГА НА НЕФТЕПРОДУКТЫ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	405
Пулатов Дилшод Хақбердиевич, Маматкулов Салимжон Рахмонкулович, Хужамурадов Аброрбек Рўзимурат ўғли, Воронин Сергей Александрович, Абдиев Мансур Мусурмонович	
OLIIY TA'LIMGA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATI: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR	410
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE NETWORK.....	416
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE NETWORK

Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich

Faculty of Economics, PhD, Associate Professor

Namangan State Technical University

email: nbahriddinov@lincolnucsf.edu

ORCID: 0000-0002-3765-5778

Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the role and strategic importance of sector in the current economic system, the mechanisms for the development of this sector in an innovative direction, the effectiveness of the mechanisms and the use of existing opportunities and resources. The article discusses the modernization of service networks, the interactive use of digital technology, the innovative business environment, and ways to support the creative production of inventors, engineers, designers, and technologists. The article is aimed at developing the service sector and bringing the service sector to new levels, as well as developing the virtual service sector.

Keywords: investment, banking, possible system, online law, economic product, service sector, innovative products, efficiency, innovation as a result of storage, modern entrepreneurship, startup business, technology, activity included in the article news. net site, innovation treatment, inventors, engineers, technologists, creative ideas, modern developments.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada sektorlashtirishning hozirgi iqtisodiy tizimdagi o'рни va strategik ahamiyati, ushbu tarmoqni innovatsion yo'nalishda rivojlantirish mexanizmlari, mexanizmlarning samaradorligi hamda mavjud imkoniyat va resurslardan foydalanish masalalari atroflicha tahlil etilgan. Maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlarini modernizatsiya qilish, raqamli texnologiyalardan interaktiv foydalanish, innovatsion biznes muhiti, ixtirochilar, muhandislar, dizaynerlar va texnologlarning ijodiy ishlab chiqarishini qo'llab-quvvatlash yo'llari muhokama qilinadi. Maqola xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish va xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini yangi bosqichlarga olib chiqish, shuningdek, virtual xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sarmoya, bank, mumkin bo'lgan tizim, onlayn huquq, iqtisodiy mahsulot, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, innovatsion mahsulotlar, samaradorlik, saqlash natijasida innovatsiyalar, zamonaviy tadbirkorlik, startap biznes, texnologiya, faollik maqola yangiliklariga kiritilgan. net sayt, innovatsion muolajalar, ixtirochilar, muhandislar, texnologlar, ijodiy g'oyalar, zamonaviy ishlanmalar.

Аннотация: В статье представлен комплексный анализ роли и стратегического значения секторизации в современной экономической системе, механизмов развития данной сферы в инновационном направлении, эффективности этих механизмов и использования имеющихся возможностей и ресурсов. В статье рассматриваются модернизация сетей обслуживания, интерактивное использование цифровых технологий, инновационная бизнес-среда и пути поддержки творческой деятельности изобретателей, инженеров, конструкторов и технологов. Статья направлена на развитие сферы услуг и вывод её на новый уровень, а также развитие виртуальной сферы услуг.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, банковское дело, возможная система, онлайн-право, экономический продукт, сфера услуг, инновационные продукты, эффективность, инновации как результат хранения, современное предпринимательство, стартап-бизнес, технологии, деятельность, включенная в статью, новостной сайт.net, инновационное лечение, изобретатели, инженеры, технологи, креативные идеи, современные разработки.

INTRODUCTION

International experience shows that the systematic implementation of innovations and advanced ideas in practice, combined with high quality of service provision, is recognized as a factor of social development and economic growth. Today, countries that are implementing innovative models of economic development and widely using “smart” technologies are achieving high rates of economic growth and strengthening their competitiveness in global markets.

These other important aspects of development are that the document emphasizes that the priority is not based on traditional production resources - raw materials, capital and labor, but on innovative developments, technological solutions, knowledge and intellectual personality. It is this aspect that shows the need to consider innovation as a strategic resource in the modern economy.

In the 21st century, the development and implementation of innovative technologies in the production and service sectors, the emergence of modern management methods, the emergence of new ones, have become a factor in the market economy. This has become a significant factor in determining the efficiency of operations, accounting and product quality, and the reason for this is that today the role of the service sector in the economic system is sharply increasing. The strategic role of this sector in economic growth is determined by the use of new scientific knowledge, intellectual resources, information and communication technologies, skills, consulting, technological advice and other high-added value. In various sectors of the economy, in this particular service sector, innovation and the standard of living of the population have become the object of scientific discussion due to their interdependence and interaction processes. Therefore, scientific research in this area is not yet carried out in a comprehensive manner. In this regard, the use of certain studies conducted by scientists, time, and the development of the service sector by V.A. Degtereva deserve due attention.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The term «Innovation» in the broad sense, initially related to the innovative activity highlighted above, was first proposed by the Austrian economist Y. Schumpeter in his work « Theory of Economic Development» in 1912¹. The most basic provisions of the innovation theory are also fully substantiated in this work.

American management expert P. Drucker developed a broader approach to innovation, namely, “Innovation is a complex system by which ideas and inventions are transformed into commercial reality for the first time. This means bringing products or services to the market, successfully introducing them into the economy².”

According to Russian economist A.I. Anchishkin, the terms³ “innovation” and “innovation” cannot be limited only to technical and technological changes. He gave this term a broad social meaning, considering innovations as an important means of developing society, and said that technical and technological innovations, having certain economic consequences, help to fight for the sales market, change the competitive environment, and thereby contribute to social development.

Another definition is as follows: “innovation is the process of introducing new things, creating, distributing and using new things (new practical tools) to fully meet the changing needs of people under the influence of social development.” E.A.Utkin⁴ defines innovation as an object introduced into production as a result of scientific research or discovery, which is qualitatively different from its predecessor.

Many scientists agree that in a developing economy and in a generally unstable economic situation, state financial stimulation of innovative activity is more acceptable, beneficial and effective. According to foreign scientist LE Mindeli, the importance of indirect methods of state support is determined, first of all, by the fact that indirect stimulation requires significantly lower budget costs compared to direct financing, and at the same time it covers a much wider range of innovative entities⁵. V.R. Tugusheva and R.R. Yunyaeva also noted that indirect stimulation requires significantly less budget funds than direct financing⁶.

Having made a more in-depth analysis of the so-called direct and indirect incentive measures, N.Yu. Krivoruchko classifies measures in the field of improving infrastructure and the regulatory and legal framework as indirect support measures, and L.E. Mindeli considers the formation of the state innovation infrastructure as direct support measures⁷.

1 Schumpeter Y. “Teoriya ekonomicheskogo razvitiya”. - M. , Progress , 1982. -455 p.

2 P. Drucker Novyy bizness.- M.: Ekonomika, 1993, p.

3 Anchishkin A. I. Science - technology - economics.- M.: Ekonomika, 1986, -35 p .

4 Utkin E.A., Morozova G.I. Innovative management. - M., Akalis, 1996. -208 p.

5 World Economic Forum: official website. Access mode: <http://www.weforum.org/>. (Access date: 01/12/24).

6 Tugusheva VR, Yunyaeva RR State incentives for crediting innovative activities in the agro-industrial complex // Izvestia of Perm State Pedagogical University. VG Belinsky. – 2011. – No. 24. – P. 469–474.

7 Fundamentals of innovation management / Ed. Zavlina PN, Kazantseva AK, Mindeli LE – M.: “Economics”, 2006. – 518 p.

In general, the work of the cited specialists on innovation and innovative activity suggests the need for research on the topic of methods of state financial stimulation of innovative activity in business enterprises. This, in turn, determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article examines and examines scientific and theoretical approaches based on the scope of the topic. Also, the research employed general scientific methods, including analysis and synthesis, to identify and summarize the ways of state funds in Uzbekistan during the time of economic reforms. The direction of the research was chosen to achieve the goal set. The research strategy was determined to thoroughly study and substantiate primary and secondary sources of information.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In our opinion, the task of developing strategic directions for ensuring innovative work in the service sector is to develop a framework for its subsequent sectors. In this regard, it is necessary to take into account the implementation of appropriate types of innovation (product, process, marketing, management, etc.) in each area.

In our opinion, innovations in the service sector are characterized by:

1	Technological innovations	Demonstrate the use of technology, demonstrate new uses, and introduce new equipment to produce new related products.
2	your support for innovation	By placing it in the consumer's possession, the contents and types of use indicated are preserved, and the quality of preservation is improved.
3	and management	business processes, introducing new methods of management, decision-making, service delivery, using new information and communication resources
4	I socio-economic	The provision of services that contribute to improving working conditions and improving the quality of life of the population, by creating their own social, economic and legal conditions for activity
5	Financial	The service sector needs new information and technologies to finance and attract investments.

The state-organized support association is being established for the transformation of our republic into a market economy with a high share of innovation and intellectual contribution to the service sector, to a country with a favorable innovation-investment environment, and to a country with a favorable market economy. The goal of the association is to fully transform the economy of our republic into an innovative model, which requires state-organized support for innovative activities in the country and the effective implementation of innovative ideas, developments and technologies in public administration, leading sectors of the economy and the social sphere.

The organizational interaction of the innovative enterprise and small innovative enterprise sector with scientific organizations and higher educational institutions is the basis for the development of production and production sectors in the region. The acquisition and systematization of innovative statistics have their own specific events, which are associated with the definitions of "innovative company", "innovative-active", "small innovative enterprise". This is due to the fact that, for example, food companies clearly assess the innovative entity in order to classify it as innovative. Innovative enterprises have become widespread in modern countries and in the modern country, and their role in the development of the market is significant. The rights of the winners of the lease of non-residential premises should be provided by enterprises that maintain their functional purpose. Before the project, documents are drawn up and taken into account when conducting competitions, it is necessary to provide assistance to the population in the production of network activities. It is recommended to do this at the beginning of retail facilities, during their construction or reconstruction.

In scientific works prepared for the topic under study, various definitions have been given to the category of "state-organized regulation and support of innovative entrepreneurship." According to GAYarin, "state-organized regulation and support of innovative entrepreneurship is a "The innovative business environment is an engineer who provides legal, political, economic, social, legal and other conditions for the activity of state bodies for the development of innovation." According to economist I.Vakhramov, the expected results from increasing the efficiency of the state's innovation and investment policy are determined by its objective conditions for the introduction of innovations, namely, the presence of a risk level, the development of new technologies, a significant reduction in the time of service processes, the compatibility of the scientific environment and the development of innovation infrastructure, the formation of an appropriate infrastructure

to facilitate scientific and research work, the need to form systems with high capital capacity for this activity, a competitive environment in the consumer market, the provision of state guarantees for small innovative enterprises, and high requirements for innovations and specialists. Achieving these goals is associated with the implementation of a general program of structural and infrastructural changes. Yudov SD emphasized that state support for innovative entrepreneurship is aimed at creating a favorable legal, tax and administrative environment to activate innovative entrepreneurship, create new jobs and increase the well-being of the population engaged in this.

The service provider's innovative entrepreneurship is dependent on many factors, the main of which is the institutional environment. The role of statehood in the process has a corresponding role. Accordingly, the development of the service provider's innovative activity is accompanied by a number of others. In our opinion, they are:

- the lack of development of relevant legislative justification for the development and operation of innovative activities of service providers;
- identify problems related to the use of investment resources in the sector;
- insufficient improvement in incentives for granting tax incentives aimed at supporting innovative activities in the sector;
- obstacles and products in the context of integrating the innovative activities of service providers;
- the interests and protection of innovative entrepreneurs are not well protected;
- the significant underdevelopment of the "market of innovative products". The importance of state innovation policy is determined by the objective characteristics of innovative processes, namely, high risk, dependence on the level of the scientific environment and innovative infrastructure, the need for large capital for scientific research and experimental design work, the need for honest and broad development of entrepreneurship in the future, high requirements for innovations, scientific and technical qualifications of personnel, etc. State support for innovative entrepreneurship is aimed at activating innovative entrepreneurship, creating new jobs and improving the well-being of the population involved in it.

The strategic goal of the concept of the development of science until 2030 is the transition of the national economy to an innovative and high-tech format, the use and proper mobilization of human resources, the volume of innovative products, investment in the areas of rapid economic growth, the improvement of the standard of living of the population, the solution of problems in the social sphere, the use of innovative products and scientific and technological solutions, the development of international scientific cooperation, the implementation of the laws "On Science and Scientific Activity" and "On Innovative Activity". In order to support and develop innovative activities in our republic, it is necessary to develop a concept of state-organized regulation of service and service-oriented innovative entrepreneurship. We, based on the practical analysis of various regions of Uzbekistan, have developed an organizational economic mechanism for supporting and developing regional service-oriented innovative activities. In our opinion, this mechanism is The specific feature is that the place is given to enterprises and organizations providing services in the region. The mechanism allows for active participation in the business-production association, which takes into account the people and the demand for innovations in the region. In a broad sense, this mechanism is necessary for the development of conditions for the development of initiatives and products - science and business cooperation in the areas of cooperation.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Currently, the procedure for integrating innovative activities into the provision of services is being restructured. Accordingly, there is a lack of methodological support for the management of innovative activities in decision-making on their implementation. This is currently If we go further, it is necessary to develop modern services to support innovative activities.

In our opinion, the development of innovative activities in modern service provision is based on the following principles:

- focusing on conducting scientific research, an important area of activity for organizations in modern service industries;
- attract small and private services to innovative activities based on technical requirements in the field;
- purchase and sale of innovative production tools for the provision of services with high customer satisfaction and economic location;
- introducing new methods and practices in the field of innovative service provision;
- individuals who promote innovative activities or who are actively involved in the organization, based on the criteria established, and the use of useful innovative resources.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Schumpeter Y. "Teoriya ekonomicheskogo razvitiya". - M., Progress , 1982. -455 p.
2. P. Druker Novyy bizness.- M.: Ekonomika, 1993, p.
3. Anchishkin A. I. Science - technology - economics.- M.: Ekonomika, 1986, -35 p .
4. Utkin E.A., Morozova G.I. Innovative management. - M., Akalis, 1996. -208 p.
5. World Economic Forum: official website. Access mode: <http://www.weforum.org/>. (Access date: 01/12/24).
6. Tugusheva VR, Yunyaeva RR State incentives for crediting innovative activities in the agro-industrial complex // Izvestia of Perm State Pedagogical University. VG Belinsky. – 2011. – No. 24. – P. 469–474.
7. Fundamentals of innovation management / Ed. Zavlina PN, Kazantseva AK, Mindeli LE – M.: "Economics", 2006. – 518 p.
8. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi "2022—2026 yillarda Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida" gifarmoni.[//www.lex.uz](http://www.lex.uz)
9. Kotler,F., Marketing management. Expresscourses.2ndedition./Translated in to English.Redacted.BojukSGSt. Petersburg:Piter,2006.-464 pages.
10. Tuxliyev I S, Hayitboyev R., Ibodullayev N.Y E., Amriddinova R S. Turizm asoslari: O'quv qo'llanma–S.:SamISI, 2010-247bet.
11. Ochilov I. Bozor munosabatlari sharoitida xizmatlarning turlari va ularning tavsifi. //Xizmat ko'rsatish, servis va turizm sohasini rivojlantirish: muammolar va ularning yechimlari.Monografiya.T.:“IQTISODIYOT-MOLIYA”,2008yil.
12. Mualliflar jamoasi. Xizmat ko'rsatish, servis va turizm sohasini rivojlantirish: muammolar va ularning yechimlari. Monografiya. Professorlar M Q Pardayevva H N Musayevlar tahriri ostida-T.:Iqtisod-moliya,2008.-194bet.
13. Farmon(2023) O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mipziyoyevning 2023yil 11sentabdagi "O'zbekiston–2030"strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi PF-158-sonli Farmoni.[//www.lex.uz](http://www.lex.uz)
14. Qaror,(2022) O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022yil 27yanvardagi "Xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishga oid qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi PQ104-sonli qarori.[//https://lex.uz/docs/584028-sonli qarori](https://lex.uz/docs/584028-sonli qarori). [//https://lex.uz/docs/584028](https://lex.uz/docs/584028).
15. N.Baxriddinov. Xo'jalik yurutuvchi korxonalarini innovatsion faoliyatni moliyaviy rag'batlantirishda xorij tajribasining o'rni. //“IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOT VA TAHLIL” ilmiy elektron jurnali, IV-son, Aprel 2025.

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100